

A Mixed Reality Interface for Human-Swarm Interaction^{*}

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Abstract. The increasing deployment of multi-robot systems underscores their potential across diverse research and applied domains. Despite advancements in robot autonomy, challenges persist in achieving full autonomy in certain scenarios. In this paper, we propose leveraging human-robot interaction to intelligently combine human and robot capabilities. By assigning a human operator the role of supervisor, robots focus on environmental data retrieval, enhancing safety and task execution efficiency. This paper presents a Mixed Reality solution utilizing the Microsoft HoloLens 2 headset, allowing a human operator to designate specific areas for a multi-robot team to reach and cover.

Keywords: Human-Robot Interaction · Mixed Reality · Multi-Robot Systems.

1 Introduction

Recent years have seen a notable growth in the deployment of multi-robot systems (MRSs), indicating their growing potential in a variety of research and applied fields [2]. One of the most extensively researched applications where MRSs are successfully used is coverage control [1], whose goal is to optimize the deployment for monitoring an area. Even though research has been moving towards increasing robots autonomy, there are still many situations where robots are unable to operate fully autonomously. An interesting approach to overcome existing limitations could be to intelligently exploit human-robot interaction (HRI) in order to combine their capabilities, instead of aiming for a complete automation of the task. As pointed out in [3], a human operator can be assigned with the role of supervisor, exploiting their intelligence and their possibly external point of view, while robots can concentrate on retrieving information from the environment and fulfill the operation. In addition, this strategy enhances safety for the human being, demanding the possibly dangerous on-field execution of the task to the robots. Recently developed Augmented Reality (AR) or Mixed Reality (MR) interfaces offer a promising approach for HRI, thanks

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to the possibility to define a shared environment where humans and robots can interact and collaborate. MR devices such as Microsoft HoloLens, in particular, offer an immersive experience to the user, allowing different types of interactions, not only limited to a touch input on a screen.

In this paper, we develop a MR solution to interact with a MRS. In our implementation, a human operator is equipped with a Microsoft HoloLens 2 headset, enabling them to designate a specific area with a desired shape to be reached and covered by the team.

2 Preliminaries

Notation and Definitions In the rest of the paper, we denote by \mathbb{N} , \mathbb{R} , $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, and $\mathbb{R}_{> 0}$ the set of natural, real, real non-negative, and real positive numbers, respectively. Given the matrix $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, we define $|\Sigma|$ as its determinant. The environment where the robots are supposed to operate will be denoted as $Q \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. An arbitrary point in Q is denoted by $q \in Q$.

Assumptions Consider a MRS composed by n robots moving in two dimensions, controlled in order to reach a specific area of the environment. We assume each robot to be modeled as a single integrator system, whose position $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ evolves according to $\dot{p}_i = u_i$, where $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the control input, $\forall i = 1, \dots, n$. We assume robots are able to localize themselves and other robots detected inside their circular sensing region, defined by a radius $R_s \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Communication among them is not allowed.

3 Background

In this section, we will briefly present the fundamentals of our control strategy. More in details, we will present Gaussian Mixture Models and coverage control, which will be used to define an environment’s probability density and to drive robots toward the specified area, respectively.

3.1 Gaussian Mixture Models

A Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) is a probabilistic model that assumes that a sample set is generated from a combination of k Gaussian distributions, each characterized by a mean point $\mu_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and a covariance matrix $\Sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ (see [4]). The overall model is created by combining these components using specific weighting factors $w_i \in \mathbb{R}_{> 0}$, with $\sum_{i=1}^k w_i = 1$. When a user draws a polygon $S \subset Q$ in the environment with a Mixed Reality (MR) device, a GMM fitting the desired shape can be estimated using *Maximum Likelihood* methods as detailed in [5]. This approach employs an *Expectation-Maximization* algorithm to iteratively determine the best parameters (μ, Σ, w) from the sample distribution.

Once the GMM has been defined, one can calculate the probability function for each individual component as follows:

$$\phi_i(q, \mu_i, \Sigma_i) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(q - \mu_i)\Sigma_i^{-1}(q - \mu_i)^T\right)}{\sqrt{|\Sigma_i|(2\pi)^d}}. \quad (1)$$

Finally, the overall probability function can be calculated as the weighted sum of each component:

$$\Phi(q, \mu, \Sigma) = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i \phi_i(q_i, \mu_i, \Sigma_i). \quad (2)$$

In our work, we utilize GMMs to specify a specific probability density so that robots are guided into the targeted areas, aiming at assigning a higher density to the region selected by the human operator. The samples set for the fitting operation is retrieved discretizing the region of interest.

3.2 Coverage Control

After explaining how the region defined by the human operator shapes the probability density, we'll now describe how this density guides robots to the target area. Our approach is based on Voronoi-based coverage control, where robots position themselves optimally to maximize coverage over the specified probability density. This technique uses Lloyd's algorithm to achieve an ideal configuration that covers as much area as possible. To make this work, we divide the entire area into cells using Voronoi partitioning, assigning specific regions to each robot. Since our robots have limited sensors and no global knowledge of their teammates' positions, we compute the Voronoi partitioning in a decentralized manner based on directly measurable data. This requires using a constrained Voronoi partitioning method as defined in [6]. Each robot, as a result of this limited Voronoi partitioning, obtains a cell $V_i \subset Q$ where it has full sensor coverage. Subsequently, every robot autonomously calculates its cell's centroid, considering the probability function (2).

$$C_{V_i} = \frac{\int_{V_i} q \Phi(q, \mu, \Sigma) dq}{\int_{V_i} \Phi(q, \mu, \Sigma) dq}. \quad (3)$$

Finally, the control action can be calculated in order to move each robot towards the centroid of its cell with a proportional law $u_i = -k_p(p_i - C_{V_i})$, with $k_p \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$.

This control strategy brings the team in an optimal configuration, maximizing the area coverage and consequently the information gathering from the environment.

4 Control Architecture

In this section, we will present the tools employed to build up the MR interface for HRI. As previously stated, the goal of our implementation is to create a

Fig. 1: (a) Hand gestures for cursor manipulation. (b) Region of interest drawn in the MR environment.

shared environment for a MRS and a human operator, in order to combine their capabilities and fulfill the task. In particular, the goal of the presented solution is to allow a human to define a desired region of interest inside the environment, and move the robots into this area in order to retrieve information, exploiting human intelligence for the high-level planning of the task while demanding the on-field execution to the robotic team.

In our work, we make use of Microsoft HoloLens 2 headset featuring a see-through display for Mixed Reality. A virtual scene has been created with Unity, featuring a virtual sphere to be used as a cursor by the operator, who can manipulate the cursor with specific hand gestures, as shown in Fig. 1a. QR codes have been placed in known locations in the real environment, to be detected by the HoloLens cameras in order to align the reference frame of the virtual scene with the real-world reference frame. While moving the sphere around, a trail is drawn to show the area that is being selected (see Fig. 1b), and the coordinates of the cursor are continuously sent to an external computer to keep track of the movement. Finally, once the elaboration system has fitted a GMM to the region that the human operator has defined, it communicates the GMM parameters to the robots, making them move in accordance with the coverage control algorithm outlined in Section 3.2. Robots and the external computer exploit ROS 2 to run the control software and to establish communication with each other.

5 Experimental Evaluation

Finally, we demonstrate the execution of an experiment where a human operator must identify a region in a real-world environment that has to be monitored by robots, with the aim of evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed architecture. In order to monitor the robots using a motion capture system, the user must wear the HoloLens 2 headset and scan a QR code to align the inertial reference frame with the global one, which is specified in the real world. Then, they can grab the virtual sphere and encircle the desired area to be reached, resulting in the final shape, as shown in Fig. 1b. Then, the external computer fits a GMM to the selected region, resulting in the probability distribution shown in Fig. 2a, where the higher attractive effect of the area encircled by the human operator is

Fig. 2: (a) Probability density associated to the drawn region of interest. (b) Final configuration of the MRS.

clearly visible. Finally, robots are controlled as described in Section 3.2. A sensing range $R_s = 2$ m is considered for each robot, and a random starting position is chosen for each of them. As we can see from Fig. 2b, the final configuration assumed by the robotic team fits the desired area defined by the operator, and robots optimally spread in order to maximize the covered surface of the region of interest.

6 Conclusions

In this work we proposed a MR solution to interact with a MRS. Our solution makes use of Microsoft HoloLens 2 headset to encircle a region of the environment to be reached by the robots. We performed a qualitative analysis of results employing real mobile robots, showing that the MRS successfully reaches the desired area. In future works, we intend to gather quantitative data to examine the effectiveness of our solution. Additionally, we plan to carry out user studies to evaluate the architecture’s usability and assess the degree to which people feel comfortable engaging with robots in a shared environment.

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